

1 **The E5 protein of high-risk human papillomaviruses is a senescence-modifying gene.**

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6 We studied total transcription following expression of low risk and high risk human papillomavirus early E5
7 protein human cells. EGFR activation by low and high risk HPVs was similar. However, interferon pathway
8 modulation was a specific property of high risk human papillomavirus E5. The genes controlled by high
9 risk HPV E5 included *IFI* family genes, MX1, oligoadenylate synthetases, RIG-I and TRIM22. The ISGs
10 controlled by high risk HPV E5 are components of the senescence program. The E5 protein of high-risk
11 human papillomaviruses is a senescence-modifying gene which cooperates with p53/Rb1 inactivation by
12 E6 and E7 to drive transformation.

13 **References**

- 14 1. Ren, Shuling et al. "HPV E2, E4, E5 drive alternative carcinogenic pathways in HPV positive
15 cancers." *Oncogene* vol. 39,40 (2020): 6327-6339. doi:10.1038/s41388-020-01431-8
16 2. Miyauchi, Sayuri et al. "Human papillomavirus E5 suppresses immunity via inhibition of the
17 immunoproteasome and STING pathway." *Cell reports* vol. 42,5 (2023): 112508.
18 doi:10.1016/j.celrep.2023.112508
19 3. Campo, M S et al. "HPV-16 E5 down-regulates expression of surface HLA class I and reduces
20 recognition by CD8 T cells." *Virology* vol. 407,1 (2010): 137-42. doi:10.1016/j.virol.2010.07.044
21 4. Trammel, Jessica et al. "Epidermal growth factor receptor-dependent stimulation of differentiation
22 by human papillomavirus type 16 E5." *Virology* vol. 590 (2024): 109952. doi:10.1016/j.virol.2023.109952
23 5. Sudarshan, Sawali R et al. "Two conserved amino acids differentiate the biology of high-risk and
24 low-risk HPV E5 proteins." *Journal of medical virology* vol. 94,9 (2022): 4565-4575. doi:10.1002/jmv.27829
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